

Local Government in Moldova

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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with the support of the Congress of Local Authorities of Moldova (CALM)

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Moldova is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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1. The System of Local Government in Moldova

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Types of Local Governments

The Republic of Moldova is organized in *rayons*, cities, villages and the Autonomous Region of Gagauzia. The administrative and territorial organization of the country is based on two levels: villages (communes), sectors (of the Chisinau municipality) and cities (municipalities) constitute the first level; *rayons*, Chisinau municipality and Balti municipality constitute the second level. Chisinau municipality is the capital city of the country and its status is regulated by the organic law. Urban localities are classified on four ranks according to a list of indicators that describe their level of social and economic development. Cities that meet specific requirements established by law could be assigned with the status of a municipality.

A total number of 32 *rayons* and 1495 localities (from which 32 are part of the Autonomous Region of Gagauzia) exist in Moldova (excluding the breakaway Transnistrian Region of Moldova). From the total list of localities, 66 are urban localities, including 53 cities and 13 municipalities and 832 are rural localities. 597 localities do not have own administration as they are part of a bigger administrative entity.

Legal Status of Local Governments

In fulfilling their competences, the local public administration authorities have autonomy, enshrined and guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, the European Charter of Local Self-Government and by other treaties to which the Republic of Moldova is a party. According to Article 109 of the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, 'public administration in the administrative-territorial units is based on the principles of local autonomy, decentralization of public services, eligibility of the local public administration authorities and consultation of citizens in the local issues of special interest.'

The public administration authorities, through whom local autonomy is exercised in villages and cities, are the elected local councils and the elected mayors. Local councils and mayors act, under the conditions of the law, as autonomous administrative authorities and manage public affairs of villages and cities. The *rayon* council coordinates the activity of the village and city councils in order to realize the public services of district interest. The *rayon* council is elected and functions according to the law.

The relations between the local public authorities are based on the principles of autonomy, legality and collaboration in solving common problems. In order to ensure local autonomy, the local public administration authorities elaborate, approve and manage autonomously their budgets and have the right to implement local taxes and to establish their amount according to the law.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

For the first-level local authorities, the following own fields of activity are established:

- urban planning and management of green areas of local interest;
- collection and management of household waste, including the cleaning and maintenance of land for their storage;
- distribution of drinking water, construction and maintenance of sewage and wastewater treatment systems;
- construction, maintenance and lighting of local public streets and roads, local public transport;
- arrangement and maintenance of cemeteries;
- administration of goods from local public and private domains;
- construction, management, maintenance and equipping of pre-school and out-of-school institutions (nurseries, kindergartens, art schools, music);
- development and management of urban gas and heat distribution networks;
- cultural, sporting, recreational and youth activities, as well as the planning, development and management of the infrastructures necessary for these types of activities;
- arranging agricultural markets, commercial spaces;
- carrying out any other measures necessary for the economic development of the administrative-territorial unit;
- establishment and management of municipal enterprises and organization of any other activity necessary for the economic development of the administrative-territorial unit;
- the construction of houses and the granting of other types of facilities for the socially vulnerable population, as well as for other categories of the population;
- organization of territorial services (stations) of rescuers and firefighters, contributing, in accordance with the law, to the protection of the cultural heritage and monuments in the administered territory.

For the second-level local public authorities, the following own fields of activity are established:

- administration of assets in the public and private areas of the district;
- planning and administering the construction, maintenance and management works of some public objectives of *rayon* interest;

- construction, administration and repair of the roads of district interest, as well as of the road infrastructure;
- organization of passenger car transport, administration of buses and car stations of *rayon* interest;
- establishing a general framework for the development of the territory at *rayon* level and the protection of the forests of *rayon* interest;
- supporting and stimulating the initiatives regarding the economic development of the administrative-territorial unit;
- elaboration and implementation of the projects of construction of the interurban gas pipelines (including the medium pressure gas pipelines), of other thermo-energetic objectives with local destination;
- maintenance of primary schools, kindergartens and high schools, vocational secondary education institutions, boarding schools and boarding schools with special regime, other institutions in the field of education that serve the population of the respective district, as well as other methodical activities from the field;
- administration of cultural, tourism and sports institutions of *rayon* interest, other cultural and sporting activities of *rayon* interest;
- administration of municipal enterprises of district interest;
- administration of social assistance units of district interest;
- development and management of community social services for socially vulnerable categories, monitoring the quality of social services;
- contribution, under the conditions of the law, to the protection of the cultural heritage and monuments in the administered territory.

Local public authorities of the first and second levels, within the limits of the law, have full freedom of action in the regulation and management of any matter of local interest which is not assigned to another authority. Other competences specific to the local public authorities can only be assigned to them by law.

The competences pertaining to the central public authorities can be delegated to the local public authorities by the first and second levels, respecting the criteria of efficiency and economic rationality. The delegation of powers may be performed by the parliament. The delegation of powers may concern all local public authorities of the first and second levels (general delegation) or only some local public authorities. The delegation of powers shall be accompanied by the provision of the necessary and sufficient financial resources for their realization.

Political and Social Context in Moldova

The resident population of the Republic of Moldova at the beginning of 2019 was 2.68 million, decreasing by 1.8 per cent compared to the same period of 2018. The main reason for the

decrease in the number of the resident population is negative net migration that increased from –24,600 people in 2014 to –48,600 people in 2018. As far as internal population movements are concerned, about 57 per cent of the population lives in rural areas. According to the 2014 census, about 17 per cent of the population lives in the capital city of the country, Chisinau municipality.

The general local elections, the 7th electoral exercise since the proclamation of the independence of the Republic of Moldova, took place in 2019 throughout the territory of the country, including in the localities of Gagauzia, except for the settlements under the control of the unrecognized administration in Transnistria. The highest number of mayors come from the social-democratic Democratic Party of Moldova (261), the former ruling party of Moldova, followed by the Party of Socialists of the Republic of Moldova (206) that are currently governing the country and representatives of the opposition electoral block ACUM (172) and SOR party (43). A total number of 112 city halls are led by independent candidates and a remaining 99 city halls are led by extra-parliamentary political parties.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, 1994

Law no 764/2001 on Administrative-Territorial Organization of the Republic of Moldova

Law no 435/2006 on Administrative Decentralization

Law no 436/2006 on Local Public Administration

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

